

A

B

$$-\frac{d[\text{NADH}]}{dt} = v = [\text{Fus}] \cdot \frac{k_{\text{cat}1} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{d1}} + k_{\text{cat}2} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{d1}K_{d2}} + k_{\text{cat}3} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{Fus}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d3}}}{1 + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{d1}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{d1}K_{d2}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{Fus}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d3}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{PdR}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d4}}}$$